

MUZEUL ȚĂRII CRIȘURILOR

CRISIA

LIV

O R A D E A • 2 0 2 4

ASPECTS ON THE URBANIZATION OF BIHOR COUNTY IN THE COMMUNIST PERIOD (II): MARGHITA AND SALONTA¹

Cristian CULICIU*

ABSTRACT

Urban development in the communist period is a vast subject, researched by many scholars from all over the World. During that time, after WWII and till 1989-1991, Eastern European cities were developed by massive industrialization, the regime's policy aiming to uniformize urban living. This happened also in Romania and Bihor County. Besides Oradea, which was the county's capital, other cities were developed and grew, and also new towns were created, even from scratch. In this paper we will see the case of a commune transformed into a city (Marghita) and that of an existing city in the beginning of the communist period, that also grew, Salonta, aiming at specific urban developments, industrialization, housing and public services.

Keywords: communism, industrialization, urban development, systematization, city living, Bihor County, Marghita, Salonta.

The urban network of Bihor County extended during the communist period through the further growth of existing cities and the development of new ones, following the emergence of industrial centers and the migratory movement. The direction and trend were common at the time to the regime's policy of increasing the population of the cities and forming a new "urban man", with the perspective of the uniformization of citizens in terms of their standard of living and day-to-day lifestyle. The county capital – Oradea, developed mainly², being the main pole for attracting investments and labor from the county, and as intensive industrialization took place in the territory, new growth poles appeared.

One of the new cities in Bihor in the communist period is Marghita, located in the northeastern part of the county, on the right bank of the Barcău River.

At the beginning of the period after WWII, corresponding to the establishment of the communist regime, Marghita went through several changes. The economic ones were most significant, in 1948-1949 the main enterprises being nationalized, after which the collectivization of agriculture began. In 1951 a collective agricultural farm and four agricultural associations were formed, among the first of their kind in the region³. In the summer of the same year, a Station of Agricultural Machinery and Tractors was also established⁴. The collectivization ended in 1962,

¹ This article follows a study on the cities of Bihor County during the communist period, the first part referring to Aleșd and Beiuș. See: Cristian Culiciu, "Aspects on the urbanization of Bihor County in the communist period (I): Aleșd and Beiuș", in *Crisia* LIII, 2023, p. 305-327.

* Țării Crișurilor Museum Oradea – Museum Complex/ University of Oradea, Center for Interdisciplinary Studies; e-mail: cristian.culiciu@yahoo.com.

² Cristian Culiciu, *Urbanismul în era „de stat”. Sistemizarea Oradiei în comunism* [Urbanism in the "state era". The systematization of Oradea in communism], Țării Crișurilor Museum Publishing House, Oradea, 2020, *passim*.

³ *Regiunea Oradea în anii democrației populare* [Oradea Region in the years of people's democracy], [1956], p. 76.

⁴ *România liberă* (Bucharest), year 9, no. 2236, December 6, 1951, p. 1.

Marghita having a joint Agricultural Production Cooperative with the villages of Cheț and Ghenetea, as well as a State Agricultural Enterprise⁵, the rayon having a total of 81 Collective Agricultural Farms⁶.

Map of Marghita in 1941 (maps.arcanum.com)

Through the administrative-territorial reform of 1950⁷, the organizing system of counties and the so-called “plasa” were abolished and replaced by the Soviet system of regions and rayons. Thus, Marghita rayon was formed in the place of the “plasa”, its center being Marghita commune, with 6157 inhabitants. Cheț village belonged to Sălacea commune and had 1320 inhabitants, and Ghenetea village belonged to Pătal commune and had 832 inhabitants. Both villages became part of the commune of Marghita.

Marghita commune and its surroundings on a map of Crisana Region from 1950 (National Archives of Romania, Bihor County branch, *Collection of plans and maps fund*)

⁵ Nicolae N. Gal (coord.), *Monografia orașului Marghita*, Editura Primus, Oradea, 2007 p. 147.

⁶ *Munca* (Bucharest), year 18, no. 4457, March 6, 1962, p. 1.

⁷ *Legea nr. 5/1950 pentru raionarea administrativ-economică a teritoriului Republicii Populare Române* [Law no. 5/1950 for the administrative-economical rayoning of the territory of the Peoples' Republic of Romania], accessible on <https://lege5.ro/Gratuit/gezdiobxgu/legea-nr-5-1950-pentru-raionarea-administrativ-economica-a-teritoriului-republicii-populare-romane>, accessed on April 22, 2024.

The urbanization of Marghita was based on the intensive industrialization of the locality. Its connection to the local electrical system also helped, 1961 the 15Kv electrical power line being put into use⁸.

At the beginning of the post-war period, a mill and an oil press operated here⁹, and the Cooperative of Cobblers and Shoemakers was established. Having 80 employees in 1948, after nationalization it became the “Record” Craft Cooperative¹⁰, with 126 employees. In ten years, the Cooperative grew to 500 employees, who worked in the footwear, carpentry and locksmith sections. The first one later turned into a factory, and the remaining sections continued their activity, diversifying them in the 1970s and 1980s with shoemaking, carpentry, tailoring, car and motorcycle repairs, TV and radio services¹¹.

The Craftsmen Cooperation Serving Complex (*Crișana*, June 21, 1963)

Also, a part of an cooperative was a furniture section, later transformed into the “Barcăul” Furniture Factory. In 1954 it was part of the “Record” Cooperative, with 13 workers making kitchen furniture. In the following two decades, the department was part of the Local Industry Enterprise and had about 200 employees. In the mid-1960s, it was also producing furniture for living and sleeping rooms, but many quality issues were found¹².

Moreover, the Local Industry Enterprise, established on September 13, 1951, had a complex activity, focused on common needs. It bore, for a short time, the name “Herbac János”, having a grain mill and a generator set for producing electricity. Later, several mineral wool, brick, knitwear, carpet, and vehicle repair workshops were established, including the aforementioned furniture section. From 1959, a foundry began operation, after a few years producing flax and hemp crushers and vices with about 1000 employees. From 1978 the company became the Auto Spare Parts Factory¹³.

⁸ *Crișana* (Oradea), year 16, no. 32, February 8, 1961, p. 3.

⁹ *Să ne cunoaștem regiunea* [Let's know our region], 1956, p. 35.

¹⁰ *Oradea Region in the years of people's democracy*, [1956], p. 49.

¹¹ Nicolae N. Gal (coord.), *op. cit.*, p. 2.

¹² *Crișana*, year 21, no. 224, September 23, 1966, p. 3.

¹³ Nicolae N. Gal (coord.), *op. cit.*, p. 167; *Crișana*, year 25, no. 189, August 14, 1970, p. 2.

On July 7, 1959, the “Bihoreana” Footwear Factory began its activity¹⁴, following the transformation of the footwear section of the “Record” craft cooperative into a factory. Initially, it operated with a single production line and 150 workers, making men’s home slippers. A new production hall was put into use in 1968-1969, when the factory’s activity was relocated from the city center¹⁵, reaching 600 workers¹⁶, and by 1988 it had five production lines, with about 1000 employees. The factory was subordinated to the Leather and Footwear Industrial Center in Bucharest, belonging to the Ministry of Light Industry. Towards the late 80s, “Bihoreana” Marghita was producing sandals, shoes, boots and home slippers, also exporting to the German Democratic Republic and the Soviet Union¹⁷.

Another factory from the same industrial field was the clothing factory, established in 1960 as a section of the “Miorița” Enterprise from Oradea, with 200 employees. After three years, it merged with the “Bihoreana” Footwear Factory, and in 1965 it became an independent factory, producing uniforms for preschoolers and students, shirts, pajamas, with 500 employees. For a short time, between 1969 and 1972, the factory was part of the Oradea Textile Plant, together with the “Miorița”, “Drum nou” and “Crișana” factories in Oradea, so that in 1971 it became the Clothing Enterprise, with over a thousand employees. After some investments in the first half of the 1970s and the start of a new production line, the number of employees exceeded two thousand, and the product range expanded to include men’s shirts¹⁸.

The Clothing Factory under construction and one of its production departments
(*Marghita în plină dezvoltare și înflorire [Marghita in full development and flourishing]*, 1977)
(*Crișana*, March 8, 1974)

The Marghita Machine Tools Factory began its activity on June 12, 1978, with the first product leaving its gates in January 1980¹⁹. The investments made here were structured over several years, suffering delays due to the lack of equipment and heat, and new capacities being commissioned in 1981 and 1982²⁰. The product range included universal milling machines, radial arm milling machines, belt conveyors, horizontal and vertical milling machines, wedge channel milling machines

¹⁴ *Flacăra* (Bucharest), year 38, no. 28, July 14, 1989, p. 18.

¹⁵ *Crișana*, year 22, no. 106, May 6, 1967, p. 2; *Scântea* (Bucharest), year 41, no. 9253, August 29, 1972, p. 3.

¹⁶ *Crișana*, year 25, no. 189, August 14, 1970, p. 2.

¹⁷ *Crisia* (Oradea), year 18, 1988, p. 907-908; Nicolae N. Gal (coord.), *op. cit.*, p. 167-168.

¹⁸ *Flacăra*, year 35, no. 10, March 7, 1986, p. 6; *Crisia*, year 18, 1988, p. 901-902; Nicolae N. Gal (coord.), *op. cit.*, p. 169.

¹⁹ *Scântea*, year 49, no. 11624, January 6, 1980, p. 1.

²⁰ National Archives of Romania, Bihor County Branch (N.A.R.B.C.B.), *Comitetul județean Bihor al P.C.R. [The Bihor County Committee of the R.C.P.]* fund, file 3/1981, sheet 139.

and centrifugal cooling pumps (16 types of machine tools in 1985²¹ and 20 in 1988²²). The maximum number of employees reached in the second half of the 1980s, was around 1400²³.

The Marghita Machine Tools Factory (*Familia*, 1989)

Other segments of the local industry were the oil and gas platform, established in 1984, with the object of exploration and exploitation of crude oil and gas deposits²⁴, and the bakery products factory, built in the second half of 1967²⁵. For the transport of goods and people, a bus depot operated within the city limits. At the end of the 1980s, it was equipped with 400 vehicles, some local public transport lines being operated by the Local Transport County Enterprise. In general, according to the press of the time, the total value of industrial production in the city would have increased from 150 million lei in 1965 to 2 billion lei in 1982²⁶ and over 3 billion lei in 1988²⁷. Throughout the communist period, the local industry was dominated by clothing production, in 1973 representing 53.3% of the total production, followed by footwear production with 16%, food production with 13% and machine building and metalworking (11%)²⁸, this last one increasing after the opening of the Machine Tools Factory.

The increase of the number of employees also rose the demand for housing. In Marghita, plots of land were allocated for building new houses, and in the early 1960s, the first apartment blocks were erected, having two floors and wood heating, on the current Piața Independenței Street, near the hospital. Of these, 16 apartments were completed in 1964-1965, far from the real needs, given that both the number and the quality of housing in the commune were below expectations²⁹.

²¹ *România liberă* (Bucharest), year 43, no. 12767, November 20, 1985, p. 3.

²² *Scântea*, year 57, no. 14370, November 1, 1988, p. 1-2.

²³ *Crisia*, year 18, 1988, p. 903-904; Nicolae N. Gal (coord.), *op. cit.*, p. 171.

²⁴ *Flacăra*, year 33, no. 44, November 2, 1984, p. 6; Idem, year 36, no. 26, June 26, 1987, p. 5.

²⁵ *Crișana*, year 22, no. 141, June 16, 1967, p. 2.

²⁶ *Ibidem*, year 37, no. 11121, December 8, 1982, p. 3.

²⁷ *Ibidem*, year 43, no. 12858, July 21, 1988, p. 3.

²⁸ Mihai Maghiar, „Dezvoltarea economico-socială a orașului Marghita în anii puterii populare” [The economic and social development of the city of Marghita in the years of people’s power], in *Trei decenii de afirmare a județului Bihor pe coordonatele socialismului* [Three decades of affirmation of Bihor County on the coordinates of socialism], Oradea, 1974, p. 200.

²⁹ N.A.R.B.C.B., *Comitetul regional Crișana al P.M.R.* [The Crișana Regional Committee of the R.W.P.] fund, file 4/1965, sheet 34.

The first apartment buildings in Marghita, situated on the nowadays Piața Independenței Street (Crișana, 1964)

Postcard – blocks of flats in Marghita in the early 1970s

Prior to the administrative reorganization at the beginning of 1968³⁰, when the county system was re-established, Marghita became a city. The new statute was conferred by Decree no. 1010 of October 27, 1967, of the State Council of the Socialist Republic of Romania³¹. In a short time, the city received the title of “industrial-agrarian center”³².

The path to accelerated urbanization was open, meaning, in addition to new industrial constructions, investments in housing stock, utilities, the road network and public space, including the educational and sanitary systems. The regime aimed to urbanize some communes in every county as much as possible, more from a political and ideological point of view, but some aspects of urban life needed to be resolved urgently in many cases.

In 1966-1970, few apartment buildings were erected in the city, 211 apartments in total, and 133 houses from private funds³³. Although solid, the buildings had finished, masonry and plumbing of poor quality³⁴. Later, in the eighth and ninth decades, the construction of blocks of flats in the city was realized by systematizing the central area, on both sides of Republicii Avenue, process favored by Law no. 58 of November 1, 1974, regarding the systematization of the territory and localities³⁵. Thus, at the end of 1975, at the Bihor County People’s Council, through the Territorial Planning Commission and the Systematization Commission with the participation of the Architecture and Systematization

³⁰ Vasile Budrigă, „Perfecționarea organizării administrativ-teritoriale a României în anii 1965-1986” [Perfecting the administrative-territorial organization of Romania in 1965-1986], in *Revista de istorie* [The History Magazine], tome 41, no. 1, January 1988, p. 52-54.

³¹ Nicolae N. Gal (coord.), *op. cit.*, p. 148.

³² Gh. Blaj, Șt. Szanto, I. Chira (coord.), *Bihor. Monografie* [Bihor. Monograph], Bucharest, Sport-Turism Publishing House, 1979, p. 96.

³³ *Localitățile județului Bihor* [The localities of Bihor County], 1971, p. 25; *Crișana*, year 24, no. 170, July 20, 1969, p. 3.

³⁴ *Constructorul* (Bucharest), year 18, no. 838, January 29, 1966, p. 3.

³⁵ *Lege nr. 58 din 1 noiembrie 1974 privind sistematizarea teritoriului și localităților urbane și rurale* [Law no. 58 from November 1, 1974 on the systematization of the territory and urban and rural localities], accessed on <https://legislatie.just.ro/Public/DetaliiDocumentAfis/351> on April 22, 2024.

Section and the County Design Institute, directions were discussed in order to draw up the new systematization plan of the city. The main categories concerned industry, agriculture, services, trade, as well as new residential and social-cultural constructions. The systematization plan for Marghita was adopted by the Bihor County People's Council by Decision no. 754 of December 31, 1975³⁶. During the same period, the local authorities estimated that, by the year 2000, the city's population would reach 26,000 inhabitants³⁷, which never happened.

In a short time, the documents necessary for the reconstruction of part of the central area and its furnishing with 312 apartments were ready, the project aiming to replace several houses in the existing built stock³⁸. The systematization project for a part of Republicii Avenue in the city center was approved by the County People's Council by Decision no. 394 of September 8, 1976³⁹. However, during the beginning of the systematization of the city, the number of apartments increased slowly, up to 432 in 1974⁴⁰, then 580 units in total in the summer of 1975, at the same time another 180 being under construction⁴¹.

Apartment buildings under construction on the corner of Republicii Avenue and Independenței Square (Crișana, April 29, 1972)

Finished apartments on the corner of Republicii Avenue and Înfrățirii Alley (Crișana, 1979)

³⁶ Archive of the Bihor County Council (A.B.C.C.), the S.A.S.T.I. [Architecture, Systematization, Technical and Investment Section] fund, file Reports of the meetings of the Executive Committee Nov. 20 – Dec. 31, 1975, sheets 332-341, 469.

³⁷ N.A.R.B.C.B., *the Bihor County Committee of the R.C.P.* fund, file 43/1974, sheet 7.

³⁸ Archive of the Oradea City Hall (A.O.C.H.), the *Întreprinderea Județeană de Gospodărire Comunală și Locativă* [The County Urban and Housing Management Enterprise] fund, file 102, unnumbered sheets.

³⁹ A.B.C.C., the *Architecture, Systematization, Technical and Investment Section* fund, file Decisions and dispositions no. 301-566, sheet 154.

⁴⁰ Mihai Maghiar, *op. cit.*, p. 202.

⁴¹ *Crișana*, year 30, no. 60, March 13, 1975, p. 2.

Newspapers show that the number of apartments would have risen to over 1000 in 1977⁴², then to 1500 in 1979⁴³ and 1600 in 1980⁴⁴, of which 355 were scheduled for finishing that year⁴⁵. In general, the buildings were typical, identical to some built in Oradea and other cities, designed by the County Design Institute. Even though they were quick to build, such buildings created monotony usually noticed by local authorities. “Unfortunately, designers don’t ask for our opinion on the blocks they design. We would have liked the designers to consider the local specifics, not to design almost all the blocks the same”, said the mayor of Marghita, Ioan Haiăș, in an interview for the *Crișana* newspaper⁴⁶.

To comply with the legal provisions and the “suggestions” coming from the head of the state, by Decree no. 20 of the State Council of February 7, 1978, the new version of the systematization plan of Marghita was approved. It established the functional areas and provided

(*Familia*, February 1978)

for a buildable perimeter of maximum 203 ha. The document also regulated road traffic, water, sewage, heat and electricity networks, as well as the height regime of the apartment buildings – 96% were to have five floors at the most⁴⁷.

After that, the Bihor County Design Institute completed the systematization project of a part of Caragiale Street (nowadays December 1 Street). Stage 1 of the plan provided for the construction of 318 apartments in 18 sections of blocks of flats with five floors,

replacing eight houses with their yards. The expropriation was done with the opposition of the owners, and the demolished buildings were in good or mediocre condition, having been built of brick and adobe. The families affected by the systematization of the area were moved to the blocks on Crinului Street, near the “Bihoreana” Factory⁴⁸. The area was then completed with 96 apartments, built following the expropriation of eight properties by Decree no. 155/June 8, 1982⁴⁹.

Also in 1978, Decree no. 214 of June 23 regarding the construction, near the “Bihoreana” Factory, of a complex of 184 apartments, two dorms for those unmarried with 608 places and a canteen with 600 seats was issued. This required the expropriation of three adobe and brick houses, in mediocre condition, some outbuildings and empty lands, including arable land. This

⁴² *Marghita în plină dezvoltare și înflorire* [Marghita in full development and flourishing], brochure, 1977.

⁴³ *Crișana*, year 34, no. 9955, March 4, 1979, p. 3.

⁴⁴ *Ibidem*, year 35, no. 10361, June 26, 1980, p. 3.

⁴⁵ *Ibidem*, no. 10251, February 7, 1980, p. 1.

⁴⁶ *Ibidem*, year 34, no. 9979, April 1, 1979, p. 1, 3.

⁴⁷ A.O.C.H., the *County Urban and Housing Management Enterprise* fund, file 87, sheets 4-5.

⁴⁸ *Ibidem*, sheets 11-15, 116, 121, 128, 138.

⁴⁹ *Ibidem*, file 100, unnumbered sheets.

land had to be “recovered” by introducing a similar area into the agricultural circuit at the local Agricultural Farm⁵⁰.

At the national level, in 1978-1979 the housing construction plan was increased to mark the 30th anniversary of the establishment of the Romanian Communist Party and its 12th Congress. For the year 1978 in Marghita 301 apartments were planned to be built, another 400 in 1979 and another 350 in 1980⁵¹. The target of the authorities was that, by 1980, the living area would reach 8.35 sqm per capita⁵². The numerous delays and high demands were putting pressure on the construction sites, so that even in Marghita the labor force outside the Construction Trust was called upon. “More than 120 young people worked on the construction sites on Saturday and Sunday”, for simple, unpaid work, such as digging foundations and laying access roads⁵³.

In the same period, by Decision no. 431/1980 of the Executive Committee of the Bihor County People’s Council, the systematization project of the central area of Marghita was approved. It served, in the 1980s, as a basis for other systematization project in the vicinity of Republicii Avenue.

The model of the central area of Marghita mainly included apartment buildings; some of them have not been constructed (*Familia*, no. 5, 1981)

Most of the blocks of flats planned in those years were built. In the summer of 1982 local press showed that there were about 2600 apartments in Marghita⁵⁴, an identical number being presented two years later⁵⁵ (it is therefore possible that the data for 1982 was exaggerated). In

⁵⁰ *Ibidem*, file 282, sheets 1-11, 16, 25-26, 89.

⁵¹ A.B.C.C., *The Architecture, Systematization, Technic and Investment Section* fund, file Decisions and dispositions no. 383-588, 1978, sheet 105.

⁵² N.A.R.B.C.B., *The Bihor County Committee of the R.C.P.* fund, file 41/1980, unnumbered sheet.

⁵³ *Crișana*, year 34, no. 9979, April 1, 1979, p. 3.

⁵⁴ *Ibidem*, year 37, no. 10996, July 14, 1982, p. 3.

⁵⁵ *Familia* (Oradea), year 20 (120) no. 4 (224), April 1984, p. 4.

addition, the city would have been enriched with 1300 new houses, built after 1965⁵⁶. At the same time, for the end of 1979, the *Munca* newspaper showed that “half of the city’s population lives in blocks of flats”, a most likely exaggerated estimate if we consider an average of two people living in an apartment⁵⁷.

Another systematization project was promoted in 1987, aimed at erecting 192 apartments in four-story blocks in the perimeter of Republicii – Garoafei Streets, replacing eight adobe and brick houses, built in the 1930s – 1940s and inhabited by 24 people⁵⁸. This project was linked to the other systematization project completed a year ago, which involved the construction of 246 apartments between Republicii Avenue and Litoralului Street⁵⁹. Of these, about two thirds were built. The last high-rise block of flats in Marghita was built by applying the expropriation Decree no. 293 from 1984, near the intersection of Republicii Avenue and Caragiale (nowadays December 1) Street, having nine floors and 52 apartments. The project provided, for a later, undefined stage, the systematization of Litoralului Street, including the furnishing of five-story prefabricated buildings. This stage has not been completed⁶⁰.

The last general systematization plan of the city was drawn up in early 1986. In the following year, local authorities and architects proposed to complete the “civic center” by 1990⁶¹. In total, by 1989, 3,250 apartments would have been built, in blocks with two to nine floors⁶², practically “half of the population” living in them, as stated by the *Crișana* newspaper⁶³, a statement more credible in 1989 than it was back in 1979. An obviously exaggerated total was expressed in the press in 1988, in an interview with the mayor of Marghita, Maria Furic – she then claimed that the city would have had “more than 4,000” apartments at the time⁶⁴.

In perspective, construction of phase 1 of the “civic center” with 150 apartments was planned to begin in 1989, with phase 2, projected by 1995 to include another 500 units. Another 250 apartments were planned to be built near the Machine Tools Factory, but these were not erected either⁶⁵.

Republicii Avenue (*Crișana*, 1986)

⁵⁶ *Crișana*, year 38, no. 11309, July 17, 1983, p. 3.

⁵⁷ *Munca*, year 35, no. 8524, December 28, 1979, p. 7.

⁵⁸ A.O.C.H., The *County Urban and Housing Management Enterprise* fund, file 97, unnumbered sheets.

⁵⁹ *Ibidem*, file 98, unnumbered sheets.

⁶⁰ *Ibidem*, file 97, unnumbered sheets.

⁶¹ N.A.R.B.C.B., the *Bihar County Committee of the R.C.P.* fund, file 2/1987, unnumbered sheet.

⁶² Nicolae N. Gal (coord.), *op. cit.*, p. 149.

⁶³ *Crișana*, year 43, no. 12858, July 21, 1988, p. 3.

⁶⁴ *Idem*, no. 12720, February 11, 1988, p. 3.

⁶⁵ N.A.R.B.C.B., the *Bihar County Committee of the R.C.P.* fund, file 19/1988, unnumbered sheet.

The areas with apartment buildings in Marghita, on Republicii Avenue and near the industrial area

The new constructions and the rise of the population meant new infrastructure and growing needs in local commerce. The dwellers of Marghita had, in 1970, 41 stores, including eating establishments⁶⁶, but many products were missing and some of the shops and restaurants were poorly maintained⁶⁷. Their number rose, in the 1980s, to around 100 shops and commercial spaces, managed by the State Mixed Commercial Enterprise and the “Bistra” Consumer Cooperative, the second one later changing its name to the Production, Purchases and Sales of Goods Cooperative⁶⁸. A significant part of them were located on the ground floors of new apartment buildings. At the same time, the city had a market.

By urbanization, investments were made in public space and public services needed increasing. Marghita had a total of 167 streets in 1967⁶⁹, the length of the network rising to 33.9 km at the end of the 1970s, of which 13.3 km were modernized roads. In a few years, the streets will have reached a modernization percentage of 70%⁷⁰, while at least 20 new streets were founded⁷¹. In 1989, the city had 62 streets, totaling around 30 km in length, of which 42 were modernized⁷². The distribution of drinking water was a rather new thing in town⁷³, with 4 km of pipes and 6.5 km of household sewers⁷⁴, in 1982 reaching a flow rate of 50 l/s, much less than the required 70 l/s⁷⁵. By 1989, the water distribution system would have reached a total length of 32 km⁷⁶. The sewage system was completed by 1980⁷⁷, and at the end of the 1970s the automatic telephone switchboard was set up⁷⁸.

⁶⁶ *The localities of Bihor County*, 1971, p. 25.

⁶⁷ *Crișana*, year 23, no. 63, March 15, 1968, p. 3; *Ibidem*, year 25, no. 28, February 5, 1970, p. 1, 3.

⁶⁸ Nicolae N. Gal (coord.), *op. cit.*, p. 176-177.

⁶⁹ Probably the total refers to streets and alleys. See: *Crișana*, year 22, no. 7, January 10, 1967, p. 2.

⁷⁰ *Ibidem*, year 34, no. 9955, March 4, 1979, p. 3.

⁷¹ *Ibidem*, year 35, no. 10361, June 26, 1980, p. 3.

⁷² *Fáklya* (Oradea), year 44, no. 271, November 16, 1989, p. 3.

⁷³ The first experimental water analysis station was opened in Salonta in 1967. See: *Crișana*, year 22, no. 7, January 10, 1967, p. 2.

⁷⁴ *The localities of Bihor County*, 1971, p. 24.

⁷⁵ N.A.R.B.C.B., the *Bihor County Committee of the R.C.P.* fund, file 7/1982, sheet 88r.

⁷⁶ *Fáklya*, year 44, no. 271, November 16, 1989, p. 3.

⁷⁷ *Crișana*, year 36, no. 10553, February 7, 1981, p. 3.

⁷⁸ Gh. Blaj, Șt. Szanto, I. Chira (coord.), *op. cit.*, p. 96.

The heating of the apartments was provided by the thermal power plant. The city also had a hotel and leisure base, as a spa destination. The treatment base for rheumatic diseases, locomotor disorders and for recovery was completed in the spring of 1979, being able to perform 300 procedures daily; the hotel complex had 104 beds⁷⁹.

Educational institutions have adapted to a growing population. At the beginning of the studied period, until 1956, two primary and secondary schools operated in the locality, one teaching in Romanian and the other in Hungarian, as well as a school for apprentices. The apprentice school was converted into a vocational school in 1949, training students to be turners, locksmiths, shoemakers, builders and tinmen. High school education was established in Marghita in 1956, in the Mixed Secondary School, later these schools being unified. By 1967, about 2,200 students were learning in town, both locals and from the surrounding villages⁸⁰. A first major investment in this field was inaugurated in 1964 – a building with 32 classrooms, workshops and laboratories⁸¹. The high school was to be transformed into an Industrial School Group, considering the need for workforce in local factories. In the 1980s, the profile of the high school was oriented towards fields such as oil extraction, mechanics, light industry, and the number of students would have reached around 1900 in 1989. At the same time, in 1961, an Agricultural Professional School was established at the Agricultural Machinery and Tractor Station⁸².

According to *The localities of Bihor County* monograph, in the 1970/1971 school year, six kindergartens, three primary and secondary schools, a high school and a vocational school operated in Marghita, the total number of preschoolers being 351, and that of students 3077⁸³.

The main building of the Marghita High School (*Bihorul în imagini* [Bihor in images], 1969)

⁷⁹ *Crișana*, year 34, no. 9979, April 1, 1979, p. 3; *Ibidem*, no. 10064, July 11, 1979, p. 1; *Ibidem*, year 38, no. 11309, July 17, 1983, p. 3.

⁸⁰ *Ibidem*, year 22, no. 273, November 19, 1967, p. 1.

⁸¹ *Ibidem*, year 19, no. 172, July 23, 1964, p. 3.

⁸² Nicolae N. Gal (coord.), *op. cit.*, p. 219-220, 237-238.

⁸³ *The localities of Bihor County*, 1971, p. 25.

The number of students rose in the following years, reaching 3447 in 1977, trained by 162 teachers. Six nurseries/kindergartens, two primary and secondary schools, a vocational school and an industrial high school for machinery operating in the city⁸⁴. Later, in 1981, a year after its initial planning, a school with ten classrooms was opened⁸⁵.

Leisure options are also part of the urban landscape. Marghita had a cinema since the 1940s, called “Apollo”, nationalized in November 1948⁸⁶, then renovated and extended in 1953⁸⁷, then again in 1963⁸⁸. In the beginning of the 1970s, the city had two cinemas, but for a short time⁸⁹. A new building for a cinema was planned in 1979, part of a systematization plan of the area around the House of Culture.

Marghita Cinema (*Crișana*, April 19, 1955)

With a capacity of 350 seats, the project was eventually abandoned⁹⁰, and five story blocks of flats was built on the targeted land. At the same time, in 1961, there was at least one hotel in the locality⁹¹.

In Marghita, in the time there was also a House of Culture with 600 seats, inaugurated on January 24, 1959 (in which the cinema was later moved), with a public library originally opened in 1950, where the courses of the Cultural-Scientific University were held⁹². On December 31, 1960, the Rayon House of Culture for young people was inaugurated⁹³.

The House of Culture of Marghita before (left) and after (right) its renovation in 1967 (postcards)

⁸⁴ *Marghita in full development and flourishing*, brochure, 1977.

⁸⁵ *Crișana*, year 35, no. 10251, February 7, 1980, p. 1.

⁸⁶ Gabriel Moisa, Sorin Șipoș, Aurel Chiriac, Radu Romînașu (coord.), *Istoria Bihorului. Civilizație, societate, economie, mentalități* [The History of Bihor. Civilization, Society, Economy, Mentalities], Țării Crișurilor Museum Publishing House, Oradea, 2018, p. 837.

⁸⁷ *Scânteia*, year 22, no. 2829, November 26, 1953, p. 2.

⁸⁸ *Ibidem*, year 32, no. 6092, December 1, 1963, p. 2.

⁸⁹ *The localities of Bihor County*, 1971, p. 25.

⁹⁰ N.A.R.B.C.B., the *Bihor County Committee of the R.C.P.* fund, file 8/1975, sheet 215r.

⁹¹ *Scânteia*, year 30, no. 5079, February 18, 1961, p. 4.

⁹² Gh. Blaj, Șt. Szanto, I. Chira (coord.), *op. cit.*, p. 238.

⁹³ *Crișana*, year 16, no. 52, March 3, 1961, p. 3. Its construction began in late July 1958. See: *Ibidem*, year 13, 179, August 1, 1958, p. 2.

As for Marghita's sanitary system, it was designed so that it could serve the locality, as well as the surrounding area, mainly the entire northern part of Bihor County / Crișana Region. In the first half of the 1950s, the local hospital operated in the old Children's Dispensary with 20 beds. Across the road there was a Birth House, the Adult Consultation Office and the Ambulance Station. In 1956, these entities moved to a single headquarters, the unified territorial hospital, led by Dr. Teodor Spoială, with 80 beds (20 for Internal Medicine, 20 for Surgery, 20 for Pediatrics, 15 for Obstetrics-Gynecology and 5 for tuberculosis cases). By expanding the buildings, in 1959 Marghita's hospital had 200 beds⁹⁴, and in 1970, 350 beds⁹⁵, after the outpatient clinic was put into use⁹⁶. Later, under the directorship of Dr. Mircea Pop, the health unit increased the quality of its services, reaching, in 1979, 700 beds⁹⁷, opening departments for intensive therapy and dentistry⁹⁸, while the Polyclinic, inaugurated in 1963⁹⁹, was operated with 40 doctors¹⁰⁰. By 1989, the local hospital had had 85 doctors and 250 other employees¹⁰¹. At the same time, in the 1980s, it had external sections in Valea lui Mihai and Popești, and factory dispensaries were opened in the city. To treat metabolic and digestive disorders, to combat sterility and heal wounds, in the mid-1970s, a swimming pool with thermal water and a communal bath were established in the city, with the capacity of 500 procedures per day¹⁰², the Polyclinic also has a Physiotherapy Section with thermal waters¹⁰³. The hotel complex next to the pool was put into use at the beginning of 1980¹⁰⁴.

Marghita Polyclinic (*Marghita în plină dezvoltare și înflorire* [Marghita in full development and flourishing], brochure, 1977)

⁹⁴ Gabriel Moisa, Sorin Șipoș, Aurel Chiriac, Radu Rominașu (coord.), *op. cit.*, p. 842.

⁹⁵ *Crișana*, year 25, no. 189, August 14, 1970, p. 2. The total needs further research, because in 1969 the same newspaper said that the hospital had 410 beds. *Ibidem*, year 24, no. 167, July 17, 1969, p. 1.

⁹⁶ Mircea Bradu, Aurel Chiriac, Gheorghe Măhăra, *Monografia județului Bihor* [The monograph of Bihor County], vol. 1, Arca Publishing House, University of Oradea Publishing House, Oradea, 2010, p. 247.

⁹⁷ Gh. Blaj, Șt. Szanto, I. Chira (coord.), *op. cit.*, p. 151.

⁹⁸ *Crișana*, year 43, no. 12858, July 21, 1988, p. 3.

⁹⁹ *Munca*, year 19, no. 4763, February 27, 1963, p. 1.

¹⁰⁰ *Ibidem*, year 32, no. 8364, December 3, 1976, p. 5.

¹⁰¹ *Făklya*, year 44, no. 271, November 16, 1989, p. 3.

¹⁰² *Scântea*, year 45, no. 10579, August 25, 1976, p. 3; *Ibidem*, year 48, no. 11405, April 22, 1979, p. 4; *România liberă*, year 37, no. 10841, September 5, 1979, p. 2. In 1972, probes were executed for locating thermal water, being found at a temperature of 65°C, the first pool being built in the same year. See: *Scântea*, year 41, no. 9204, July 10, 1972, p. 2.

¹⁰³ *România liberă*, year 39, no. 11371, May 21, 1981, p. 2.

¹⁰⁴ *Munca*, year 36, no. 8530, February 8, 1980, p. 5.

A pharmacy also operated in the city, the former Cerbul de Aur pharmacy, nationalized in 1949 and renamed Pharmacy no. 15, belonging to Centrofarm. In 1972, the unit moved to a new space, on the ground floor of an apartment building¹⁰⁵.

The urbanization of Marghita was also reflected in the number and composition of the population. The increase was due to both immigration and a very good birth rate. Moreover, in the early 1970s, Marghita had one of the highest birth rates in Bihor County – 20.7%, as well as the best migratory increase – 19.1%¹⁰⁶. The total population of Marghita, excluding the component villages, evolved in the mentioned period, as follows¹⁰⁷:

The population density was average for Bihor, increased because of the construction of collective housing, being in 1972, 171.1 inhabitants/km². Regarding the number of employees, we notice a growth supported by industrial investments. In 1950-1951, almost 1000 people worked in the town¹⁰⁸, while the job offer was small. The growth of the industrial sector, but also of the agricultural sector and of public institutions meant the rise of the number of employees, until 1970, to 7,795, of which 6,336 were workers, a little over half (3,417) working in industry¹⁰⁹. Later, in 1982, the number of employees reached 11,400¹¹⁰, a little over 70% working in industry¹¹¹.

¹⁰⁵ Manuela Bianca Pașca, *Istoria farmaciilor din Bihor – de la începuturi până în zilele noastre* [The history of pharmacies in Bihor – from their beginnings to nowadays], University of Oradea Publishing House, Oradea, 2013, p. 153-154.

¹⁰⁶ I. O. Berindei, Gr. P. Pop, *Județul Bihor* [Bihor County], Bucharest, Publishing House of the Academy of the Socialist Republic of Romania, 1972, p. 74.

¹⁰⁷ www.kia.hu/konyvtar/erdely/erd2002/bhetn02.pdf, accessed on April 26, 2024.

¹⁰⁸ Mihai Maghiar, *op. cit.*, p. 199; *Crișana*, year 35, no. 10216, January 8, 1980, p. 3.

¹⁰⁹ *The localities of Bihor County*, 1971, p. 24.

¹¹⁰ *Crișana*, year 37, no. 10996, July 14, 1982, p. 3.

¹¹¹ *Ibidem*, year 35, no. 10361, June 26, 1980, p. 3.

Another city that the regional / county authorities turned their attention to is Salonta. Located in the southwestern part of Bihor, crossed by the Culișer Stream, the locality was already a city (urban commune) at the beginning of the communist period, the second one in Bihor after Beiuș, Oradea being classified as a municipality¹¹². After 1945, the emphasis here too was on creating a centralized and planned economy, including modernizing the city and attracting new residents.

Map of Marghita in 1941 (maps.arcanum.com)

The nationalization of the main productive units and the cooperativization of agriculture marked the beginning of the socialization of Salonta's economy. By Law no. 119 of June 11, 1948¹¹³, the "Podsudek" Canning Factory became a property of the state¹¹⁴. A year later, the collectivization of agriculture began¹¹⁵, with the establishment of the "Red Flag" Collective Agricultural Farm¹¹⁶ and an agricultural association¹¹⁷. There was also a poultry complex.

The share of agriculture in Salonta's economy remained high throughout the entire communist period, at the end of 1970 the State Agricultural Enterprise having 5213 ha of agricultural land (2496 ha arable), and the three Agricultural Cooperatives had a total of 7,616 ha of agricultural land, of which 6,293 ha were arable. Cereals were mainly cultivated (43%), sugar beet, potatoes, vegetables, 120 ha being intended for fruit growing¹¹⁸. Later, the three Agricultural Cooperatives united into one¹¹⁹.

¹¹² Gabriel Moisa, Sorin Șipoș, Aurel Chiriac, Radu Rominașu (coord.), *op. cit.*, p. 809.

¹¹³ *Lege nr. 119 din 11 iunie 1948 pentru naționalizarea întreprinderilor industriale, bancare, de asigurări, miniere și de transporturi* [Law no. 119 from June 11, 1948 for the nationalization of industrial, banking insurance, mining and transport enterprises], accessed on April 27, 2024 on http://www.cdep.ro/pls/legis/legis_pck.htm_act_text?id=1575.

¹¹⁴ Gabriel Moisa, Sorin Șipoș, Aurel Chiriac, Radu Rominașu (coord.), *op. cit.*, p. 836.

¹¹⁵ In Salonta Rayon, the collectivization of agriculture was finished in February-March 1962. See: *Scântea*, year 31, no. 5450, February 25, 1962, p. 1.

¹¹⁶ *Crișana*, year 6, no. 130, June 6, 1950, p. 1; *Ibidem*, year 8, no. 308, December 31, 1952, p. 2; *Ibidem*, year 10, no. 133, June 7, 1955, p. 2.

¹¹⁷ The "August 23rd" Agricultural Association was founded in 1952. See: *Scântea*, year 24, no. 3380, September 6, 1955, p. 2.

¹¹⁸ *The localities of Bihor County*, 1971, p. 28.

¹¹⁹ *Crișana*, year 26, no. 25, January 31, 1971, p. 1, 3; *Ibidem*, no. 26, February 2, 1971, p. 2; *Scântea*, year 53, no. 13042, July 29, 1984, p. 2.

Mechanized agriculture in Salonta (*Bihorul, 30 de ani pe drumul socialismului [Bihor, 30 years on its road to socialism], 1974*)

Through the administrative changes of 1950 the former “plasa” were abolished and rayons were created. Salonta Rayon had its center in the locality with the same name, which in that year had 14,447 dwellers. The town did not have any other localities in its component.

Salonta on a map of Crișana Region in 1950
(N.A.R.B.C.B., the plans and maps collection)

The urbanization of Salonta, in the sense understood by the socialist system, was based on the growth of industrial activity. The city was connected to the national energy system in February 1962 by putting the 15 Kv Salonta – Oradea power line into operation¹²⁰.

The meat processing industry began in Salonta in 1896. After nationalization, the local canning factory was called “Prodaliment”/ “Prodexport”, and in the 1950s several production lines were installed here¹²¹. In 1971, the Meat Industrialization Enterprise had 496 employees, a

¹²⁰ *Ibidem*, year 31, no. 5448, February 23, 1962, p. 1.

¹²¹ *Crișana*, year 6, no. 76, April 1, 1950, p. 5; *Oradea Region in the years of people's democracy*, [1956], p. 31-32.

year later holding the largest share in Bihor's food industry – 29.3%¹²². The mills were also nationalized, then being brought under the authority of the City Agricultural Service, with 70 employees¹²³.

In the 1950s, a craft cooperative was producing furniture fittings¹²⁴, in 1959 being unified with another furniture workshop, thus founding the Rayon Wood Industry Enterprise¹²⁵. It maintained its activity in the following years, operating in 1971 with 318 employees¹²⁶. In 1977, “Mobila” Salonta became a department of the Wood Industrialization Enterprise of Oradea.

Local industry units also operated in the city, such as the “Energia” Cooperative which, in the mid-1950s, was manufacturing cooking stove accessories, household items, caterpillar scissors, coastal hammers, having five repair departments in the city¹²⁷. At the same time, the “Progresul” Enterprise, also established in the mid-1950s, produced brooms, and the “Drapelul Roșu” Craft Cooperative was producing clothing¹²⁸. Another Cooperative, called “Volga”, was making shoes¹²⁹. About one million lei were invested in the Bread Factory in 1960-1961¹³⁰, being finished two years later¹³¹.

By expanding the workshops, “Progresul” diversified its activity, and in 1967 it became the Auto Parts Factory, then “Metalul”¹³². In 1968-1969 the factory assimilated new products¹³³, then in 1974 it took over some other similar entities, but in 1977 it split again¹³⁴. “Metalul” was producing auto spare parts, metal cabinets, various forgings, exhaust drums and suction boxes for diesel-electric locomotives¹³⁵, boilers for heating homes¹³⁶, as well as tools, having, in 1971, 759 employees¹³⁷, and in 1982 – 1100 employees¹³⁸. The workforce was provided, in part, by training students at the vocational school in Șimleu Silvaniei, but also locally¹³⁹.

¹²² *The localities of Bihor County*, 1971, p. 27; I. O. Berindei, Gr. P. Pop, *op. cit.*, p. 120.

¹²³ Dánielisz Endre, *Salonta în secolul XX* [Salonta in the 20th century], Prolog Publishing House, Salonta, 2009, p. 94.

¹²⁴ *Oradea Region in the years of people's democracy*, [1956], p. 45.

¹²⁵ Dánielisz Endre, *Salonta in the 20th century*, p. 116.

¹²⁶ *The localities of Bihor County*, 1971, p. 28.

¹²⁷ *Oradea Region in the years of people's democracy*, [1956], p. 49-50. The “Energia” Cooperative was founded in 1945 by several tanners from the locality, who were joined by locksmiths, blacksmiths, tinsmiths, coppersmiths and plumbers. See: Dánielisz Endre, *Salonta in the 20th century*, p. 95.

¹²⁸ *Let's know our region*, 1956, p. 34-35. The cooperative has been established in October 1949 by tailors of the “Cootex” Cooperative section from Oradea. It was later merged with the “Progresul” Enterprise. See: Dánielisz Endre, *Monografia municipiului Salonta în date. Cronologie locală, culturală și urbanistică* [The monograph of Salonta municipality in dates. Local, cultural and urbanistic chronology], 2003, p. 60.

¹²⁹ *Crișana*, year 6, no. 72, March 26, 1950, p. 5.

¹³⁰ *România liberă*, year 18, no. 5010, November 23, 1950, p. 1; *Crișana*, year 16, no. 37, February 14, 1961, p. 2; N.A.R.B.C.B., *The Crișana Regional Committee of the R.W.P. fund*, file 3/1960, sheet 97.

¹³¹ *Ibidem*, file 51/1963, sheet 10.

¹³² Dánielisz Endre, *Salonta in the 20th century*, p. 114.

¹³³ *Crișana*, year 24, no. 12, January 16, 1969, p. 2.

¹³⁴ Gabriel Moisa, Sorin Șipoș, Aurel Chiriac, Radu Rominașu (coord.), *op. cit.*, p. 873.

¹³⁵ I. O. Berindei, Gr. P. Pop, *op. cit.*, p. 110.

¹³⁶ *România liberă*, year 39, no. 11262, January 13, 1981, p. 1.

¹³⁷ *The localities of Bihor County*, 1971, p. 28.

¹³⁸ *România liberă*, year 40, no. 11851, December 7, 1982, p. 3.

¹³⁹ N.A.R.B.C.B., *The Bihor County Committee of the R.C.P. fund*, file 7/1970, sheet 43.

The interior of the Auto Parts Factory in Salonta
(*Salonta în plină dezvoltare și înflorire* [Salonta in full development and flourishing], 1977)

Significant investments in Salonta's industry were made in the 1960s and 1970s. The Auto Parts Factory was expanded, in 1974 the Cotton Weaving Plant was under construction¹⁴⁰, starting its activity in the next 1-2 years (the plant had about 800 employees in 1982¹⁴¹), a Sibiu salami Factory (1974) and a poultry slaughterhouse belonging to the State Agricultural Enterprise¹⁴². Thus, the value of local industrial production would have increased in 1975 compared to 1970 by 47.2%¹⁴³.

There was also a small clothing factory and a shoe workshop, as well as several greenhouses and solariums within the local Agriculture Production Cooperative. In the mid-1980s, the "Viitorul" Cooperative produced shoes for the domestic and foreign markets¹⁴⁴, and the "Metalul" Factory had opened a caravan assembly line¹⁴⁵. The "Deservirea" Craft Cooperative had 20 workplaces in the city and about 300 employees in 1971¹⁴⁶, while the population was supplied with consumer goods through the "7 Noiembrie" Cooperative (later renamed the Goods Supply and Sale Cooperative). The first Alimentara self-service unit was opened in town across the road from the City Hall, in 1960¹⁴⁷.

In total, as stated in a propaganda material from 1984, the total value of industrial production in Salonta was, at the end of the previous year, 1.8 billion lei, "3.5 times higher than in 1965 and about 15 times higher than in 1950"¹⁴⁸.

¹⁴⁰ *Crișana*, year 29, no. 129, June 2, 1974, p. 1.

¹⁴¹ *România liberă*, year 40, no. 11851, December 7, 1982, p. 3.

¹⁴² Gh. Blaj, Șt. Szanto, I. Chira (coord.), *op. cit.*, p. 108.

¹⁴³ N.A.R.B.C.B., *The Bihor County Committee of the R.C.P. fund*, file 1/1975, sheet 139.

¹⁴⁴ *Crișana*, year 40, no. 11929, July 18, 1985, p. 3.

¹⁴⁵ *Munca*, year 37, no. 8606, July 10, 1981, p. 7.

¹⁴⁶ *The localities of Bihor County*, 1971, p. 28.

¹⁴⁷ Dánielisz Endre, *Salonta in the 20th century*, p. 132-133; *Scânteia*, year 29, no. 5007, December 3, 1960, p. 1.

¹⁴⁸ *Familia*, year 20 (120), no. 5 (225), May 1984, p. 4.

The Salonta Cotton Weaving Plant, exterior and interior
(*Salonta in full development and flourishing, 1977*; I.O. Berindei, Gr.P. Pop, *Bihor, monograph, 1979*)

The growth of the industrial segment attracted new residents to Salonta, thus the housing stock needed increasing. After the nationalization of housing, an emergency solution was the distribution of rooms for workers and their families, but the option was not viable and lowered the quality of life of the beneficiaries. In the 1950s, the authorities allocated plots for the construction of houses, a land used for this purpose being that of the former cattle market. The first house was built here in 1954, later the built-up area expanding¹⁴⁹.

Especially after 1960, the solution for solving housing needs was apartment building. The first one was built in 1961 on Școlii Street, intended for state officials¹⁵⁰. Thus, two of the first blocks of flats in Salonta were erected across the road from the Ciunt Tower. They were finished late, both due to design omissions and underfunding¹⁵¹, the buildings being of very poor finishing quality¹⁵². Also, the nearby market was moved to the outskirts of the city, so that in its place a new park would have been arranged. Three years later, the documentation for another 28 apartments was prepared¹⁵³, and between 1966 and 1970, a total of 144 apartments and 170 houses were built in the city¹⁵⁴. It was also the period when the construction of apartments began in the vicinity of the train station.

Two of the first apartment buildings erected in Salonta (*Crișana, March 13, 1966*)

Other blocks were built in the central area following the expropriation of several houses and annexes, with the related lands, on Republicii Street and the neighboring areas, according

¹⁴⁹ Dánielisz Endre, *The monograph of Salonta*, p. 61.

¹⁵⁰ *Ibidem*, p. 64.

¹⁵¹ N.A.R.B.C.B., *The Crișana Regional Committee of the R.W.P. fund*, file 4/1965, sheet 18.

¹⁵² *Ibidem*, sheet 61.

¹⁵³ *Ibidem*, file 16/1964, sheet 235.

¹⁵⁴ *The localities of Bihor County, 1971*, p. 28; *Constructorul*, year 19, no. 24, June 17, 1967, p. 3.

to Decree no. 50 from February 23, 1974. The affected owners were compensated in money and were allocated housing from the state fund, some of them not agreeing to the expropriation. On the 6,655 m² of land, six blocks with 196 apartments and commercial spaces were designed, with a construction deadline of 1974-1975¹⁵⁵. In the same period, the Executive Committee of the County People's Council approved the systematization project for the central area, by Decision no. 457 of August 16, 1975¹⁵⁶. Those years meant significant changes in urban systematization, so in the context of the emergence of the Law of systematization from 1974, at the county level, the "balancing" of the urban network in Bihor was discussed, through the accelerated growth of the small cities and a lower speed of development of Oradea. Thus, Salonta would have reached around 36,000 inhabitants in the year 2000, the second most populated urban center after the county capital¹⁵⁷. This population has never been reached. At the same time, in 1975 a new systematization plan of the city was developed.

Apartment buildings on nowadays Mărășești Street (*Crișana*, March 5, 1971)

Housing construction accelerated after the mid-1970s¹⁵⁸. Through a Decree of February 7, 1978, the systematization plan for Salonta was approved. It included the delimitation of the functional areas, the buildable perimeter totaling 845 ha, the sketch of the main and secondary streets, the water supply and sewage systems, and the heating and electricity systems. As for the new buildings, 95.4% would be built with a maximum of five stories and only 4.6% with more than that¹⁵⁹. Basically, only one apartment building of the second category was erected.

In a short time, in March, the expropriation of some constructions (brick houses) began on Republicii Street, to furnish the street with five story blocks with 100 apartments¹⁶⁰.

In total, in the second half of the 1970s, 1,400 apartments would have been built in the city¹⁶¹, including a eight-story block (mentioned above, 1977), with increased attention being

¹⁵⁵ A.O.C.H., *The County Urban and Housing Management Enterprise fund*, file 293, unnumbered sheets.

¹⁵⁶ A.B.C.C., *The Architecture, Systematization, Technic and Investment Section fund*, file Executive Committee Nov. 20 – Dec. 31, 1975, sheet 469.

¹⁵⁷ N.A.R.B.C.B., *The Bihor County Committee of the R.C.P. fund*, file 43/1974, sheet 7.

¹⁵⁸ A.B.C.C., *the Architecture, Systematization, Technic and Investment Section fund*, file Executive Committee Nov. 20 – Dec. 31, 1975, sheet 469.

¹⁵⁹ A.O.C.H., *The County Urban and Housing Management Enterprise fund*, file 87, sheet 5.

¹⁶⁰ *Ibidem*, file 93, unnumbered sheets.

¹⁶¹ Gh. Blaj, Șt. Szanto, I. Chira (coord.), *op. cit.*, p. 94.

paid to the 1979 plan, when the authorities wanted to mark the 30th anniversary of the proclamation of the republic, and the 12th Congress of the Romanian Communist Party, held in that year. The plan included 323 apartments in 1978, 222 in 1979 and 300 in 1980¹⁶², the authorities' target being that the living area in the city would reach 8.18 m² per capita by 1980¹⁶³. For this, the Construction Trust has set up a production base of prefabricated slabs for apartment buildings¹⁶⁴. In an interview for *Crișana* newspaper, the mayor of Salonta, Cseh Zoltán, showed that workers from local factories, even retirees, were sent to work on the construction sites.

New apartment building under construction in the city center (*Crișana*, 1979)

One of the blocks built in front of Salonta Train Station (*Crișana*, 1981)

The number of apartments in Salonta quickly increased, although their quality was pretty low. 1500 apartments would have been put into use in the city by 1982, to which about 400 houses, built in the last ten years, were added¹⁶⁵. By 1983, the number of

¹⁶² A.B.C.C., the *Architecture, Systematization, Technic and Investment Section* fund, file Decisions no. 383-588, 1978, sheet 105.

¹⁶³ N.A.R.B.C.B., The *Bihar County Committee of the R.C.P* fund, file 41/1980, unnumbered sheet.

¹⁶⁴ *Crișana*, year 34, no. 9973, March 25, 1979, p. 1.

¹⁶⁵ *Ibidem*, year 37, no. 11124, December 11, 1982, p. 1.

apartments in Salonta would have risen to 1633, located in blocks with three to eight floors¹⁶⁶. The total would have exceeded 1800 units by the summer of 1985¹⁶⁷, so that in 1986 it was mentioned that after 1965, “almost two thousand apartments and individual houses” had been built in the city, meaning that “almost a third of the 22,000 dwellers of Salonta live in a new home”¹⁶⁸. At the same time, in those years, out of the 126 households located outside the buildable perimeter, 68 were displaced inside it¹⁶⁹. The last two micro-neighborhoods of blocks were built in the perimeter of the current Oradiei – Rákoczi Ferenc – Zilhány Lajos – Octavian Goga Streets, respectively in the corner of Republicii and Moricz Zsigmond Streets.

According to the press, in the last reference year, 1989, the number of “new” (i.e., completed after 1965) apartments and houses reached 2300¹⁷⁰. Some of the blocks had commercial premises, so the retail area of the city increased by 1984 with 4800 m² and with 1250 m² of public catering units¹⁷¹. The last draft of the city’s systematization plan was made in 1986. A year later, the “civic center” of the city was proposed to be completed in 1990¹⁷², but the project was abandoned.

In fact, the approximately 300 apartments around the train station and the Furniture Factory were not built either. Until 1995, a significant number of apartments were planned in Salonta: 800 in the “civic center”, 380 in the Tudor Vladimirescu area, and another 1180 units in other areas of the city¹⁷³. Some of the buildings were equipped with commercial premises.

Apartments built in the late 1980s on Oradiei Street (*Fáklya*, July 22, 1989)

¹⁶⁶ *Familia*, year 20 (120), no. 5 (225), May 1984, p. 4.

¹⁶⁷ *Crișana*, year 40, no. 11819, March 10, 1985, p. 2; *Ibidem*, no. 11929, July 18, 1985, p. 3.

¹⁶⁸ *Ibidem*, year 41, no. 12169, April 30, 1986, p. 3.

¹⁶⁹ N.A.R.B.C.B., *The Bihor County Committee of the R.C.P. fund*, file 2/1987, unnumbered sheet.

¹⁷⁰ *Crișana*, year 44, no. 13168, July 21, 1989, p. 3.

¹⁷¹ *Familia*, year 20 (120), no. 5 (225), May 1984, p. 4.

¹⁷² N.A.R.B.C.B., *The Bihor County Committee of the R.C.P. fund*, file 2/1987, unnumbered sheet.

¹⁷³ *Ibidem*, file 19/1988, unnumbered sheet.

The locations of apartment buildings in Salonta

An important component of Salonta's urbanization was the development of utility networks and public services. This meant modernizing the streets, by paving them and building sidewalks, activities carried out with the help of skilled workers, but also of young people or neighbors by "patriotic work". Spitalului Street was almost finished, and the modernization of Fântânilor Street was about to begin, also with the modernization of the road to the abattoir planned. At the same time, a sidewalk was being built between the Power Plant and the fuel warehouse¹⁷⁴.

The Craftsmen Cooperation Serving Complex (*Crișana*, September 24, 1964)

In 1971, the street network had a total length of 65 km (which was maintained until 1989), of which 61 km were lit and 10 km were modernized with asphalt. Until 1984, the length of the

modernized streets reached 27.1 km¹⁷⁵. The public space was urbanized by rethinking some destinations. In 1950, the space reserved for the market in the city center was reorganized and transformed into a public plaza, and later into a park.

The water supply was done through wells; in the early 1970s the city was having problems with water supply, both for factories and population¹⁷⁶. After the completion of the adduction, in 1974, and following other investments, the network reached 17.8 km in 1984, 20 km in 1986 and 26 km in 1989. However, the flow rate was insufficient, in 1982 being 36 l/s, compared to the required 60 l/s¹⁷⁷. A 1000 m³ water castle was built to store drinking water¹⁷⁸. As for the sewage system, in addition to the installation of the network (11 km long in 1989¹⁷⁹), in 1976 the sewage treatment plant was put into use. Heating was poorly developed and served some blocks of flats, in 1989 the distribution system totaling 4.5 km¹⁸⁰. Salonta also had public transport, established in 1959, with a fleet including, in 1971, seven buses and four taxis, used in the city, in Mărțișaz and Mădăras¹⁸¹. In 1975, the network had 16.5 km bus lines, carrying around 1,019,000 passengers annually¹⁸². Finally, in January 1983, a new automatic telephone exchange system with 800 lines was completed¹⁸³.

The Territorial Hospital of Salonta in the mid-1980s (photo by the Oradea Construction Trust)

The medical field had to cover growing needs. In 1948, the State Hospital in Salonta was split into two departments, one for Surgery and another for Internal Medicine, with 30 beds each¹⁸⁴. After a few years, a Pediatric department was also established¹⁸⁵, and by 1983 the total

¹⁷⁵ *Familia*, year 20 (120), no. 5 (225), May 1984, p. 4.

¹⁷⁶ N.A.R.B.C.B., the *Bihor County Committee of the R.C.P.* fund, file 7/1970, sheet 44.

¹⁷⁷ *Ibidem*, file 7/1982, p. 89.

¹⁷⁸ *Familia*, year 20 (120), no. 5 (225), May 1984, p. 4; *Crișana*, year 41, no. 12169, April 30, 1986, p. 3; *Ibidem*, year 44, no. 13168, July 21, 1989, p. 3.

¹⁷⁹ *Ibidem*.

¹⁸⁰ *Ibidem*.

¹⁸¹ *The localities of Bihor County*, 1971, p. 27.

¹⁸² Gh. Blaj, Șt. Szanto, I. Chira (coord.), *op. cit.*, p. 150.

¹⁸³ *Crișana*, year 40, no. 11819, March 10, 1985, p. 2.

¹⁸⁴ Gabriel Moisa, Sorin Șipoș, Aurel Chiriac, Radu Romînașu (coord.), *op. cit.*, p. 842; Dánielisz Endre, *The monograph of Salonta*, p. 71.

¹⁸⁵ *Let's know our region*, 1956, p. 60.

number of beds rose to 200. A year later, press mentioned the existence of 225 beds in the city hospital and another 250 in the new hospital¹⁸⁶, that also had 66 doctors¹⁸⁷. Besides the hospital, in Salonta, in 1971, there were three medical constituencies, a general dispensary, a factory dispensary, and a territorial polyclinic¹⁸⁸ (in use since the beginning of the 1950s¹⁸⁹).

In Salonta there were also three pharmacies. One was the former Hungarian Crown pharmacy, nationalized in 1949 and renamed Pharmacy no. 17. The second one, the former Arany János pharmacy, was renamed Pharmacy no. 18, moved in 1978 to one of the new apartment buildings near the train station. The third one, formerly named Speranța (Rémeny - Hope), after nationalization functioned as a closed-circuit unit of the Territorial Hospital¹⁹⁰.

The number and size of educational institutions increased. The teaching activity was disrupted during the Second World War and during the establishment of the communist regime, functioning with fluctuations. A reorganization of local education followed. Nurseries were established, and elementary schools became primary and secondary schools. The “Arany János” and “King Mihai I” high schools were abolished, replaced by the Agricultural Technical Secondary School and the Agricultural Professional School, that later became the Agricultural School Group, then the Agricultural High School. Moreover, in the 1950s, when farms were founded, they were given a high importance, and until the 1980s the Agricultural High School was equipped with a teaching farm, a repair hall, mechanical workshops and a greenhouse¹⁹¹. The Agricultural Technical Secondary School took the name of Arany János in 1957¹⁹².

At the end of the 1953/1954 school year, 1250 pupils would have studied in the four elementary schools in Salonta¹⁹³. Later, in 1971, the local education network included 12 kindergartens with 543 children, ten elementary schools with 2,150 students, a general culture school with 580 students, and an agricultural high school with 373 students¹⁹⁴. By 1986, the total number of students enrolled in Salonta’s education system would have risen to approximately 5,600¹⁹⁵. Because we are talking about the communist period, when political-ideological education was compulsory in various forms, a branch of the Political University operated in the city, which held some courses for adults.

The main building of Elementary School nr. 2 of Salonta (*Cincinalul 1966-1970 în Bihor* [The 1966-1970 five-year plan in Bihor], 1971)

¹⁸⁶ *Familia*, year 20 (120), no. 5 (225), May 1984, p. 4.

¹⁸⁷ *Fáklya*, year 44, no. 172, July 22, 1989, p. 3.

¹⁸⁸ *The Localities of Bihor County*, 1971, p. 28.

¹⁸⁹ *Oradea Region in the years of people’s democracy*, [1956], p. 108.

¹⁹⁰ Manuela Bianca Pașca, *op. cit.*, p. 162-173.

¹⁹¹ *Scântea*, year 41, no. 13925, May 30, 1987, p. 4.

¹⁹² Dánielisz Endre, *Salonta in the 20th century*, p. 142-145; *Se dezvoltă și înflorește Regiunea Crișana* [Crișana Region is developing and flourishing] [n.y.], p. 45.

¹⁹³ *Scântea*, year 23, no. 3057, August 21, 1954, p. 1.

¹⁹⁴ *The Localities of Bihor County*, 1971, p. 28.

¹⁹⁵ *Crișana*, year 41, no. 12169, April 30, 1986, p. 3.

We also note some cultural aspects. The Transylvania Cinema, in existence before 1948, was nationalized, and in 1960 the construction of a new cinema with 334 seats began, inaugurated on February 19, 1962¹⁹⁶. The Cultural House had, in late 1951, a hall with 800 seats for concerts and shows, a library with books and six chess tables, an exhibition room and radio (its manager was Szölösi Lajos). It also had a traditional music band and a dance and theater group¹⁹⁷. In 1984, the House of Culture had 600 seats and a Trade Union Club with 350 seats¹⁹⁸. Meanwhile, the town library raised its collections to over 30,000 books in 1966¹⁹⁹.

In Salonta there was also the “Arany János” Memorial Museum in the Ciunt Tower of the former citadel of Salonta. Both the Museum and the Ciunt Tower were reorganized in the 1950s, the tower was connected to electricity, and in 1956 a plan was drawn up to increase the collections. Of course, the museum was ideologically aligned with the communist regime’s demands, and in 1957 the first permanent exhibition was organized, comprising albums, books and photo reproductions. In 1963, the museum was visited by 11,153 people, while it organized eight exhibitions both in Salonta and in Gepiu and Tinca²⁰⁰. New consolidation and modernization work took place in the Ciunt Tower in 1972. The museum was reopened on June 17, 1973²⁰¹. In early 1988, an art gallery was also opened in the city²⁰².

Postcard with aspects of the “Arany János” Memorial Museum in the 1960s (zvb.com)

The population of Salonta had a small growth in the communist period, slower than in the other cities in the county, probably because the authorities did not put much emphasis on it, since it was already a city from the previous decades. In 1948, the city had 14,200 inhabitants, of which

¹⁹⁶ Dánielisz Endre, *The monograph of Salonta*, p. 65; *Scântea*, year 31, no. 5445, February 20, 1962, p. 1.

¹⁹⁷ *Crișana*, year 7, no. 292, December 14, 1951, p. 2.

¹⁹⁸ *Familia*, year 20 (120), no. 5 (225), May 1984, p. 4.

¹⁹⁹ *Crișana*, year 21, no. 64, March 18, 1966, p. 2.

²⁰⁰ *Ibidem*, year 19, no. 21, January 26, 1964, p. 2.

²⁰¹ Dánielisz Endre, *The monograph of Salonta*, p. 62, 69; *Crișana*, year 28, no. 143, June 19, 1973, p. 2.

²⁰² *România liberă*, year 46, no. 13537, May 16, 1988, p. 2.

the majority, 86.6% were Hungarians, and 12.6% were Romanians²⁰³. In 1956 the total number of residents had risen to 16,274²⁰⁴. In 1972, the migratory increase in the city was negative (-0.7‰), which indicates the tendency of leaving the city rather moving in. The population density was 108.2 inhabitants/km², below the county's average²⁰⁵. By 1979, the population of the “agro-industrial city” of Salonta had risen to 20,099 inhabitants²⁰⁶.

The main share in the total population of Salonta remained of Hungarians, as can be seen in the graph below²⁰⁷. The increase in the number of Romanians was relatively small, but increased the city's population, while the number of Hungarians remained constant.

As for the occupations of the residents of Salonta, in 1970 the majority were employed in agriculture – 42.3%, followed by workers in industry (32.9%) and those in services (24.8%)²⁰⁸. The number of employees increased in the post-war period. In 1970, 5,992 people were working in the city, of which 4,601 were workers in industry, and 260 were commuters²⁰⁹. The active population of Salonta would have risen to around 10,000 people in 1977²¹⁰, so that in 1984 it reached around 16,000, the share of those working in industry reversing with that of farmers, respectively 32% employed in industry, 14% in agriculture and 17% in services²¹¹. Salonta's factories would have employed some 9,300 workers in the summer of 1989²¹².

Part of the urban complex of Bihor County, the towns of Marghita and Salonta became, over time, two of the county's most important localities. Industrialization turned them into polarizing centers, and urbanization raised the quality of life and the standard of living of the inhabitants, generating, however, specific problems and additional needs. The lack of basic public services, especially in the 1980s, although the infrastructure was there, is a common paradox in Romania in that time. The systematization of the two cities, although it contributed to urban diversification and the appearance of public utilities, created disturbances in the constructive fabric, but increased the population.

²⁰³ Dánielisz Endre, *Salonta in the 20th century*, p. 108.

²⁰⁴ Mihai Morgovan, „Schimbări în structura socială a județului Bihor” [Changes in the social structure of Bihor County], in *Bihor. Trecut, prezent, perspectivă* [Bihor. Past, present, perspectives], 1969, p. 47.

²⁰⁵ I. O. Berindei, Gr. P. Pop, *op. cit.*, p. 74.

²⁰⁶ Gh. Blaj, Șt. Szanto, I. Chira (coord.), *op. cit.*, p. 91.

²⁰⁷ www.kia.hu/konyvtar/erdely/erd2002/bhethn02.pdf, accessed on March 12, 2024.

²⁰⁸ I. O. Berindei, Gr. P. Pop, *op. cit.*, p. 86.

²⁰⁹ *The Localities of Bihor County*, 1971, p. 27.

²¹⁰ *Salonta in full development and flourishing*, brochure, 1977.

²¹¹ *Familia*, year 20 (120), no. 5 (225), May 1984, p. 4.

²¹² *Fáklya*, year 44, no. 172, July 22, 1989, p. 3.